

THE ROLE OF LOGORHYTHMIC IN WORKING WITH CHILDREN WITH HEARING IMPAIRMENTS

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ABSTRACT

This article aims to highlight the specific place of logorhythmic when conducting correctional work with children with hearing impairments.

KEYWORDS: *Speech, Speech Therapy, Rhythm, Auditory Cain, Special Pedagogy, Speech Disorders, Principle, Hearing Analyzers.*

INTRODUCTION

Logorhythmic is a special technique aimed at solving a number of problems related to the child's speech, coordination and hearing. Regular training will help to cope with the most common problems and save the child from many difficulties in later life. Logoritm for children is a way of playing with children who use music, tools and verbal elements. Of course, such corrective classes are held by specialists in kindergarten, but parents should not shift all responsibility to speech therapists-it is important to practice at home to consolidate the result. In addition, the form of play is fun for children. Logoritm classes are games or exercises to imitate adults along with specially selected music. That is, the child listens to the teacher or parents, sees what he is doing, then repeats what he said and did. Young children respond best to rhyming speech, but this is not necessary: any funny, interesting stories will help. The main goal of logorhythmic for children is the correction or development of speech skills. With its help, you can save the baby from speech problems such as Stuttering, pronunciation problems, too slow or too fast speech. At the same time, any speech therapy game develops several processes at once.

Logoritmics is a game technique for working with children that combines music, movements and lyrics of a poem or song.

Logarithmic activities include:

- walking or walking to music;
- games for the development of breathing;
- exercises for articulation;
- Rhythmic tasks;
- Speech exercises;
- Finger games.

Goals and objectives of logarithmic:

The main goal of logorhythmic is to develop the child's speech and eliminate speech disorders. For this, logarithmic exercises include the following tasks:

- □ Develop a sense of rhythm and tact;
- □ Teaching correct speech breathing;
- □ Improve overall and fine motor skills;
- □ Development of attention, memory and auditory perception;
- □ Inclusion of facial expressions and gestures in the child's speech;
- □ Teaching the smoothness of pronunciation of words and phrases.

The connection of the rhythms of movement and speech speech therapists believe that movement and speech are closely related. More precisely, motor and speech rhythms.

Rhythmic movements are easy to remember and reproduce them "automatically". And their motor rhythm is associated with the tempo of pronouncing words (speech rhythm).

That is, if you teach a child to rhythmic movement and correct pronunciation of words, he will be able to speak in the same measure and calmly in everyday life.

Types of exercise:

Logistic exercises are very diverse. The lesson can be structured in such a way that you often use games to help correct the speech problem.

For example, if the child stutters, you should add more breathing, tempo, and rhythm exercises to the activity. And if the baby is not given the pronunciation of certain sounds, it is worth noting articulation exercises and exercises to correct sound pronunciation. Exercises for the development of breathing, voice and articulation. These exercises develop voice strength, improve articulation, and teach correct breathing for fluent speech.

The problem of speech development and motor coordination in preschool children with hearing impairment is associated with the fact that these components are the main ones in the organization of correctional and pedagogical work with children in special preschool educational institutions.

When carrying out physical education and wellness work with children with hearing and speech defects, the main emphasis should be on revealing the individuality of the child, creating an individual correction and development program based on a comprehensive study of his development. Features of its development. To do this, it is necessary to know the general theoretical laws of a child with developmental disabilities, to guide them in pedagogical work. Various disorders in the development of a deaf child are not only the result of limited access to sound stimuli. Here, as a direct result, only disorders in the development of speech are observed. Speech acts as a means of interacting people with the outside world. Violation of such a link leads to a decrease in the information received, which affects the development of all cognitive processes, thereby primarily affecting the process of mastering all types of motor skills. The

main pathology can lead to a chain of consequences, which appear, become the causes of New disorders and come together.

The development of psychomotor skills in logarithmic lessons is carried out at an unconscious, voluntary level. The development of the Motor sphere helps to regulate speech. All qualifications obtained in logarithmic lessons are strengthened in speech material. Classes are conducted by a defectologist teacher with a musical instrument; musical accompaniment can also be performed by the music director. The duration of classes depends on the age of the children and ranges from 20 to 35 minutes. The content of motion and speech material varies depending on the degree of formation of movement and speech abilities. At the beginning of the correctional course, motor skills and abilities are developed, and then Speech work is built on this basis.

The effectiveness of the logarithmic rhythm is explained by the existing relationship between the child's movement activity and the development of speech. The formation of movements occurs with the participation of speech, the rhythm of which (especially poems) contributes to the development of motor skills.

Logorhythm for children is necessary for the formation of correct and clear speech. Many children learn to pronounce sounds for a long time, they pronounce words vaguely. If the baby does not choose the right corrective exercises, he will be under pressure then problems will arise:

Broken speech; isolation (the child is embarrassed that he does not pronounce words clearly, and if they do not understand him or laugh at him, he can stop communicating);

Complexes are formed that interfere with the development of socialization and communication skills.

Training in logorhythmia is carried out taking into account the individual characteristics of the child. These are samples. Adults show what to do, and the child repeats. Exercises include:

March and walk (in a certain rhythm);

Exercises that promote breathing and articulation;

Gymnastics for muscle tone;

Tongue twisters;

Counting exercises;

Singing;

Playing children's musical instruments;

Rhythmic movements;

Exercises for the development of fine motor skills (finger gymnastics).

If the lesson is conducted under the accompaniment of music, then the tones that reflect the emotional state are correctly selected. Marsh, rhythmic songs are suitable for walking.

Logistic exercises are diverse. The selected correctional work is compiled depending on the age of the child and his needs, individual characteristics. In training, they use not only music, they learn poetry and songs. Toys and pictures are used to diversify training, to interest children.

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